

HIGH TEMPERATURE ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING OF POLY ARYL ETHER KETONES (PAEK) COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Metallic additive manufacturing has been making significant progress in the aerospace and automotive fields with new lightweight designs, cheaper costs and faster production time avoiding machining, milling or welding. In comparison, the polymeric additive manufacturing has found most uses in less critical or lower performance applications due to limitations in materials choices.

However, recently, the powder bed fusion technology known also as laser sintering received a boost through the introduction of high temperature laser sintering (HT-LS) system, EOSINT P800 and high temperature powder materials, HP3 Poly Ether Ketone (PEK) and 150PF Poly Ether Ether Ketone (PEEK). The PAEK polymer family which includes PEK and PEEK materials has high temperature resistance, high strength, excellent mechanical resistance and high wear resistance. As with the majority of the additive manufacturing processes, one advantage offered by the HT-LS process is the design freedom, which allows fabrication of highly complex structures unachievable through any other subtractive manufacturing process.

This study presents recent developments in high temperature laser sintering of composites with focus on glass filled PEK (PEK/GB) and graphite platelet filled PEEK (PEEK/GP) materials. The hardness and thermal stability of the glass filled PEK structures has been improved without losing any of the tensile strength performance.

The graphite filled PEEK powder shows an improvement in tensile strength and strain, graphite acting as reinforcement as well as a good energy absorbent agent which leads to enhanced sintering of parts without enhanced shrinkage or distortion of parts.

1 INTRODUCTION

The family of Poly Ether Aryl Ketone (PEAK) polymers includes high melting temperature semi-crystalline polymers ($> 300^{\circ}\text{C}$), with excellent mechanical performance, thermal stability, biocompatibility, good wear and chemical resistance such as PEEK, PEK and PEKK.[1,2,3,4,5] Due to their unique characteristics, these polymers and their composites have been extensively investigated in terms of structure, properties and processing [6,7,8,9,10] through conventional manufacturing techniques and have been used in industry, automotive, aerospace and medical implants applications. Incorporation of glass into PEEK has been mostly studied for bearing applications as sliding materials where glass is added primarily as non-reinforcing filler [11,12,13, 14,15] to allow achieve low friction and wear rates. PEEK has been reinforced with various types of carbon structures including carbon fibre, graphite and CNTs to further increase its electrical [22], thermal [16,17, 18,19,20] or mechanical performance, such as prolonged fatigue stress and strain characteristics [21]. The main manufacturing methods employed for fabrication of these composite was injection and compression moulding.[22,23,24]

LS process offers a high degree of design freedom, which cannot be achieved through conventional manufacturing methods. Highly complex structures can be fabricated through LS process. The combination of high performance materials with LS as manufacturing process is unique and can open a wide range of opportunities in high temperature composite applications. This paper presents for the first time a study of PAEKs reinforced composites manufactured using the commercial high temperature laser sintering equipment, EOSINT P800.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

The materials used for fabrication were PEK HP3 and PEEK150PF powder supplied by EOS and Victrex plc, respectively. PEK HP3 was mixed with Potters Spherglass 2000 CP3 glass beads in an 80/20% ratio by weight. The glass beads had a coating designed to promote the adhesion with polymers with polar function groups such as ether, esters, amides, ketones, and sulfone. [25] The glass reinforced PEK powder was prepared by using a drum on an EOS electric powder mixer. PEEK 150PF powder was thermally treated in oven at 250°C for 24hr before mixing with graphite platelets (GP), which was supplied by Easy Composites. The graphite was added at 1% and 5% loadings to the PEEK powder. The composite powder was prepared similar to the glass/PEK using an electric powder mixer. The mixed powders were sieved on EOS powder sieve with a $245\mu\text{m}$ mesh screen and used for laser sintering.

2.2 High temperature laser sintering

The high temperature laser sintering (HT-LS) process was carried out in a reduced build mode using the EOSINT P800 system. A description of the build chamber modes and the PEEK processing parameters are available in previous publications. [26] Tensile specimens were built according to ISO527-2. The building positions of samples are illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: The building positions of PEK and PEK/GB composite (left) and PEEK and PEEK/GP composite (right) in the chamber.

2.3 FTIR

A Bruker Matrix FTIR was used to determine the absorbance values of the PEEK/graphite dry mixed powder at the wavelength of 943cm^{-1} , which is equal to the wavelength of CO_2 laser beam equipped on EOSINT P800.

2.4 Mechanical test

The tensile tests were performed on a Lloyds EZ20 machine with a crosshead speed of 2 mm x min^{-1} for all samples. 20 samples were tested. Hardness testing was performed on a digital micro-hardness tester FM-1e (Future-Tech Crop. Japan) the indentation force used was 300gf, 10s. The lengths of diagonal left by the indenter were measured, and the Vickers hardness (HV) was calculated from the equation:

$$HV=1.854F/d^2$$

Where F is the force in Kgf applied to the diamond and d is the average length of the diagonal left by the indenter in mm.

2.5 Coefficient of thermal expansion

For thermal expansion tests, laser sintered parts were cut down into cubic specimens of approximate $3 \times 3 \times 3\text{ mm}$. The samples were measured along all three directions X, Y and Z in order to investigate the thermal expansion dependence of the building direction. The X, Y and Z directions as a function of the building direction are shown in Figure 1. Specimens were annealed in oven for 1hr at 160°C to release any internal stress before conducting thermal expansion measurements. The tests were conducted in a Mettler Toledo TMA 40. A negligible force of 0.002 N was applied using a 3 mm flat quartz probe. To obtain the coefficient of thermal expansion, two heating cycles were applied on each specimen. In the first heating cycle, specimens were heated from 30°C to 300°C at a heating rate of $5^\circ\text{C x min}^{-1}$ in air, held at 300°C for 10 minutes, then cooled down to 50°C at $10^\circ\text{C x min}^{-1}$ cooling rate. During the second heating cycle, the specimens were heated from 50°C to 300°C at $5^\circ\text{C x min}^{-1}$ in air. The thermal scan recorded during the second heating cycles were used to calculate the CTE below glass transition temperature, α_g , and the CTE above glass transition temperature, α_y .

2.6 Microstructure characterization

Microstructure analysis of various powders and the fracture surface of sintered samples were carried out by secondary electron microscopy SEM (Hitachi S-3200N, Japan). The secondary electron images were taken under 25 KV acceleration voltages.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 PEK/GB composite

Figure 2(a) and (b) shows the SEM image of glass beads and PEK powder, respectively. The glass beads have almost perfect spherical shape, while the PEK powders have an irregular appearance. In spite of its irregular shape, the HP3 PEK powder dispersed well during manufacture. The addition of the glass beads however improved the flow and spreading characteristics of powder in laser sintering process due to their spherical shape.[27]

Figure 2: (a) SEM image of glass beads and (b) SEM image of the HP3 PEK powder

Figure 3 shows the stress-strain curve and hardness of LS-PEK and LS-PEK/20%GB composite. The addition of the glass beads to the PEK had no negative influence on the tensile strength and strain, which suggests a good interfacial bonding between the glass beads. The presence of the glass beads increased the hardness of the LS-PEK/20%GB composite. The LS-PEK/20%GB composite showed a 7% increase in hardness when compared with pure LS-PEK.

Figure 3: Stress-strain curve and Vickers hardness of LS-PEK and LS-PEK/20%GB composite

The fracture surface of LS-PEK in Figure 4(a) show a multi-layered structure consisting of two distinct morphologies: (1) a homogeneously sintered structure where the presence of individual particles is lost completely and (2) a dense and fully sintered layer where the presence of individual particles is still clearly visible. The layered structure is an inherent effect of the manufacturing process. A similar structure has been noticed by Zarringhalam et al., when investigating the microstructure of laser sintered nylon 12. [28, 29] Increasing energy input can help diminish creation of large differences between X, Y and Z but cannot eliminate them completely. The fractured surface of the LS-PEK/20%GB composites is presented in Figure 4(b), the glass beads were embedded in the polymer matrix without being damaged or pulled out. This result suggests a good interface bonding between the glass beads and PEK matrix as the coating on glass beads is compatible with PEK matrix.

Figure 4: SEM image of sintered materials (a) PEK HP3 and (b) PEK/20%GB composite

Table 1 presents the thermal expansion measurements of the LS-PEK and LS-PEK/20%GB above and below the glass transition temperature as a function of the building direction. The increase in temperature through the glass transition led to a significant increase in CTEs due to increase of molecular movement. The thermal expansion values of the LS-PEK/20%GB composite below and above the glass transition (α_g and α_r) were lower than the LS-PEK. This indicates the presence of glass beads in the matrix improved the thermal stability of PEEK. It is also noticed that the laser sintered samples show anisotropic thermal expansion. The thermal expansion in X and Y directions were similar but higher than those in Z direction. It could be that the layering effect restricts the free expansion across Z direction, the layers expanding against each other, creating some internal compression stress. In contrast, along X or Y direction, each layer has the same direction of thermal expansion and more freedom to expand.

CTE	LS-PEK	LS-PEK/20%GB
$\alpha_{g,x}$ (ppm °C ⁻¹)	51.0±0.82	45.3±0.47
$\alpha_{g,y}$ (ppm °C ⁻¹)	51.0±0.82	45.0±0.82
$\alpha_{g,z}$ (ppm °C ⁻¹)	49.0±0.82	44.7±0.94
$\alpha_{r,x}$ (ppm °C ⁻¹)	138.7±2.36	116.3±0.47
$\alpha_{r,y}$ (ppm °C ⁻¹)	136.3±1.25	116.0±0.82
$\alpha_{r,z}$ (ppm °C ⁻¹)	124.0±2.45	105.3±3.30

Table 1: Coefficient of thermal expansion measured from LS-PEK and LS-PEK/20%GB

3.2 PEEK/GP composite

The FTIR absorbance and reflectance of neat PEEK, graphite and PEEK/graphite composites are shown in Figure 5. The graphite platelets (GP) show significantly higher FTIR absorbance than PEEK150PF powder. The absorption of mixed powder increased with increasing amount of graphite. Stress-strain curves of sintered samples show that the addition of 1% and 5% GP led to 15% and 36% increase in tensile strength, respectively. It is also noticed that the strain% increases with increasing of graphite amount, PEEK/5% GP shows approximately 40% increasing of the tensile strain. The addition of graphite platelets can promote the laser absorption, increases the temperature of the powder bed and improves the fusion of the polymer powder. [30, 31, 32] A better fusion of the polymeric powder is expected to lead to dense parts with improved strength. It is possible that the incorporation of the graphite changed the crystal structure of the matrix, making the polymer deform in a different way and increase the strain. Moreover, the GP could also act as reinforcement and delay the crack propagation during tensile test. Diez-Pascual et al. discussed unusual melting and crystallization

behavior of PEEK and PEK with carbon fibres (CF), carbon nano-fibres (CnF) and graphite and found an increase in strain for certain combination of matrix and reinforcement.[35]

Figure 5: FTIR absorption of various powders and the tensile stress-strain curves of various sintered materials.

Figure 6(a)-(c) show the morphology of PEEK and GP used for fabrication of the composite. Figure 6(d) shows how the PEEK particles are coated with GP after dry mixing, which could effectively improve the laser absorption and transfer the heat to PEEK particles.

Figure 6: SEM images of (a) dry mixed PEEK/GP powder, (b) GP, (c) high magnification image of GP and (d) high magnification image of mixed PEEK/GP powder.

Figure 7 shows the fracture surface of sintered PEEK and PEEK/GP composite parts with various GP loadings. The neat LS-PEEK has a similar layered structure as LS-PEK (Figure 7(a)). The layered structure seems to disappear in the PEEK/GP composites as seen in Figure 7 (b) and (c). This result suggests that the addition of graphite improved the fusion between layers as a result of enhanced laser

absorption. Figure 7(d) shows the graphite platelet partially pulled out of the matrix as reinforcement filler of the composite and gives also an indication of the orientation of the graphite platelets in the fabricated composites, orientated along the x-y plane.

Figure 7: The fracture surface image of laser sintered materials (a) PEEK,(b) PEEK/1%GP composite, (c) PEEK/5%GP composite and (d) high magnification image showing GP protruding from fracture surface

4 CONCLUSION

This study achieved, for the first time, manufacture of PEK/GB and PEEK/GP composites using high temperature laser sintering. In comparison with the laser sintered PEK parts, the LS-PEK/20%GB composite had an improved hardness (7% increase) and reduced CTEs (9-12% reduction below T_g and 15-16% reduction above the T_g). Addition of glass beads had no negative effect on the tensile strength. The thermal expansion of LS-PEK and LS-PEK/20%GB composite was anisotropic. The CTE values in Z direction are lower than those in the X and Y directions. This could be related to the multi-layered structure. Incorporation small amount of GP enhanced the laser absorption of powder and increased the tensile strength as well as tensile strain of the composites. LS-PEEK/5%GP composite had 36% strength improvement and a 40% increase in tensile strain.

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